

Women in Medical Profession the Present Status and the Requirement for Education

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Gone are the days when women were considered to be suitable only for managing homes and rearing children. Opportunities are available in plenty for women to enter into professional life and be self-dependent. In India, women’s participation in unorganised sectors was very high earlier. But due to rapid development in social, economic, technological and political field, women started acquiring professional education enthusiastically and contributed to the welfare of the industrial and social life. The professional courses received by women a few decades ago facilitated the forthcoming generations to follow the trend of the previous generation at a higher velocity and pursue all kinds of technical education that are regarded to be eminent professions. One such very much coveted discipline is the medical profession.

The prestige or status enjoyed by the medical doctors is superior than that of many other professions. This status is given to the doctors because of the technical knowledge they possess. Therefore doctors too concentrated only on the medication treatment of the patient. But at present, the entire social situation has changed. At global level, a new perspective has emerged. The World Federation of Medical Education has prescribed the role of doctors and their professional integrity in future. It defines 1) professionalism, 2) doctor as a communicator, educator and researcher, 3) doctor as a manager of healthcare within society, 4) community health leader and, 5) promote health and prevent illness as the professional integrity of the doctors in future*.

*Stefan Lindgren and David Gordon, “Role of the Doctors and the competencies Expected from the Doctor of the Future of World Fender action of Medical Education (wfme.org).

The federation also points out continuous professional development is expected for the doctors by “learning how to teach, how to lead and how to disseminate knowledge and good practices for the general benefit of the society”. Therefore the medical education itself should inculcate the medical students with the good attributes of social responsibility.

High quality and technical knowledge are required in hospitals for which again a superior quality education should be provided to the doctors while they undergo the course for four years. These standards are expected by the whole society because the welfare of the community, economic activities and the well-being of the people rely on the medical field. Health is regarded as an essential human capital and it could be achieved holistically only if the medical field performs its responsibilities satisfactorily.

It appears for the general public that, in certain urban areas and multi-specialty hospitals, there are many doctors to cater to the needs of our community. But in the real situation, India has less number of doctors when compared to other countries. World Health Organization (WHO) has fixed specific standards on doctor-patient ratio, which is not the case in India. In India, the present status and the actual requirement are yet to be achieved.

Aim and Methodology

With this background idea, the present paper aims:

1. to provide data on standards set by WHO on human resources in hospitals and
2. the existing status in India, and to explain the need for more doctors and nurses to educate the public on health issues.

WHO Standards and Indian Healthcare System: Doctor–Patient Ratio

According to the recommendations of World Health Organization (WHO), one doctor is required per 1,000 population. That means India needs 4,97,189 more doctors to meet the WHO standards. As per information provided by the Medical Council of India, there was a total of 10,22,859 MBBS (Modern Medicine) doctors registered with the MCI. After considering attrition, it gives doctor-population ratio of 0.77:1,000 as per current population estimate of 1.33 billion. The Government has proposed to increase the number of doctors in the country to improve the doctor–population ratio. According to the health ministry, the existing doctor- patient ratio is one doctor for 2,000 patients, and the target is one doctor per 1,000 people. India has nearly 7.5 lakh registered doctors, of whom 5.5 lakh are in active service.

As per the Health census and Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, the overall doctor-patient ratio in India is 1:1800, but it is not uniform all over the country.

Variation prevails between States* as given below.

Delhi- 1:2203

UP - 1:19962

Tamil Nadu - 1:9544

Kerala - 1:6810

Karnataka - 1:13556

Andhra Pradesh - 1:10189

*Madav Deo, 'Doctor population Ratio of India the Reality' in Indian Journal of Medical Research .137(4): 632-635, April-2013.

Sanjay Zodpa et al.,* in their similar article after explaining the disparity between states the WHO standard could be achieved only in 2027.

Comparable figures in other countries are as follows:

Australia, 3.374:1,000;

Brazil, 1.852:1,000;

China, 1.49:1,000

France, 3.227:1,000

Germany, 4.125:1,000

Russia, 3.306:1,000
USA, 2.554:1,000
Afghanistan, 0.304:1,000
Bangladesh, 0.389:1,000
Pakistan, 0.806:1,000.

Medical Colleges in India

Currently, in India there is a total of 479 medical colleges with an intake of 67,218 MBBS students every year. This implies that for 1,000 Population, India has less than one doctor. Further, with an annual intake of 67,218 MBBS students, India will reach WHO standard of 1:1,000 doctor (only modern medicine)—population ratio within next few years. The Government is planning to double the availability of undergraduate and postgraduate seats. This will meet a target of 80,000 UG and 45,000 PG seats in India by 2021.

* Sanjay Zodpa et al., Allopathy doctors in India Estimates Norms of Projections in Indian Journal of Medical Research, April 2018.

In India, women constituted 51 percent of the students joining medical colleges, cornering 23,522 seats in 2014-15 compared to 22,934 men. The topper of NEET-2018 was a female.

More medical colleges with additional seats must be opened. As there is an acute need for continuous education and specialization in medical faculty, provision for post-graduation should be introduced. An important observation made by the researcher is female doctors outnumber male doctors. Over the last five years India has produced 4,500 more females than male doctors.

Rural India

Our country has a sharp differentiation between its rural and urban areas. The requirement, population structure and social condition are so varied between them that more doctors have to be posted in rural areas. The data shows: In rural India, only 37 percent of people have access to health facilities within a 5 km distance. For specialised treatment people have to visit urban hospitals. India also has the lowest number of physicians per 10,000 populations among BRIC countries, the report revealed. Nearly seventy five percent of Healthcare organisations, are located in urban areas, serving only twenty eight percent of the Indian populace. Seventy percent of India's population lives in rural areas, and a significant percentage of that population lacks access to healthcare. In a country with 3 percent of its physicians living in rural areas and 25 percent in semi-urban areas. Rural India has one-fourth the doctors as compared to urban areas. Taking these statistics into account, Indian government has commenced new medical colleges to produce more medical graduates.

Reproductive Health scenario and need for New outlook

At this juncture, a crucial factor has to be taken into account. It is the reproductive health of women in India. Here are ten of the main issues regarding women's health.

- Cancer
- Reproductive Health
- Maternal Health
- HIV
- Sexually Transmitted infections
- Violence against women
- Mental Health
- Non-communicable disease

Being young
Getting Older

In India, due to cultural and social factors, the female population has to be given health education and awareness. The tradition of early marriage, low level of female literacy, large families, frequency of deliveries, spacing of children are hurdles to improve the health status of women. The negative influence of these factors has to be imparted not only to the reproductive age group and married women but also to adolescent's girls. Hence we need more doctors trained to educate women on these issues relating to reproductive health. There are around 70,000 practising Obstetrics and Gynecologists lesser than the standard requirement. These doctors must be trained to teach women for a healthy life.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has commended India's progress in reducing maternal mortality ratio (MMR) by 77%, from 556 per 10000 live births in 1990 to 130 per 10000 live births in 2016. This progress puts India on track towards achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target of MMR below 70 by 2030.

India's Infant Mortality is higher than the global average. India has reduced its infant mortality rate (IMR) by 42% over 11 years from 57 per 1,000 live births in 2006 to 33 in 2017. The Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1978 raises the legal age at marriage from 15 to 18 years for girls, and from 18 to 21 years for boys.

Health Education for the Community

The World Health Organization defined Health Education as "compris[ing] [of] consciously constructed opportunities for learning involving some form of communication designed to improve health literacy, including improving knowledge, and developing life skills which are conducive to individual and community health". The purpose of health education is to have positive impact on the health behaviour of individuals and communities as well as the living and working conditions that influence their health. It is also far less expensive to prevent disease, illness or injury. So, health education and health literacy enable people to take better care of themselves. The importance of health education impacts many areas of wellness within a community, including:

- Chronic disease awareness and prevention
- Maternal and infant health
- Tobacco use and substance abuse
- Injury and violence prevention
- Mental and behavioural health
- Nutrition, exercise and obesity prevention

According to National Health survey among the health care professionals, the doctors alone are capable of taking ultimate responsibility for deciding clinical emergencies. International Labour Organization* while specifying the role of medical doctors include emphasis maintain of mental health of patients other than the clinical treatment. It states that health care professional requires other attributes like good community skills empathy of integrity.

Educating women, on reproductive health and creating awareness on health issue for the general public is the big responsibility of the doctor in addition to their patient care and treatment process. Doctors have more liability than any other profession in health education because they only possess technical knowledge of health.

Assess patients health care needs taking into account their personal social circumstances suggest preventive measures. Under the changing outlook of medical profession, the female doctors are expected to be more patient-oriented. The reproductive health issues information regarding pre and post-natal care, and nutritional needs of children has to be taught to the women especially in

rural areas, to lead a hygienic and healthy life. The medical course itself should address these essential needs.

*Medical care Recommendation 144 (No 69) International Labour Organization (Preamble – 66 to 74)

Nursing Profession

Although doctors have medical expertise, they cannot be placed fully responsible for patient care and health education. Doctors should be assisted by the nurses in this respect. The nurse-patient ratio is a number to describe the number of patients assigned to each nurse. Nurse-patient assignments are based on the acuity or needs of the patient for nursing care. In critical care units such as the ICU (intensive care unit), the ratio may be 1:1 for the sickest patients or 1:2 or 1:3 for patients who are acutely ill but stable. On general care units, the nurse to patient ratio is higher, for example, 1:5 or 1:8 depending on the type of unit and the needs of the patient. This type of nurse-patient ratio is based on guidelines from professional organisations and accreditation bodies, but is also fluid based on the needs of the individual patients at a given point in time.

Currently, India has only 1.7 nurses available per thousand populations against the WHO recommendation of 2.5 nurses per thousand populations. In other words the country is short of 2.5 million nurses. The situation is complicated by declining number of student enrolments and meager educational facilities. Registered Nurses and Midwives are 26,2718; Auxiliary Nursing Midwives 56,630 and Healthvisitors are 11,1180.

The WHO has fixed up doctor-nurse ratio as 3:1. But in India it is stated as 5:1 which means that we need more number of nurses in proportion to doctors, as we need more doctors in proportion to our country's population. India is in a condition to produce more doctors and nurses to meet the WHO standards. It is possible only by opening more government colleges for under-graduation and post-graduation of medical students. Since there is a lack of definitive nursing colleges, incompetent and unskilled students pass out from the college. When healthcare institutions recruit nursing professionals with inadequate intelligence and proficiency, patient care will be in peril. In return this tarnishes the reputation of the healthcare institution. Positive efforts should be made to open approved Nursing colleges with good teacher and training in all aspects of medical treatment. The nurse plays a paramount role in educating the rural and illiterate patients. They are considered to be community educators. They commit to teach and persuade the public on HIV, Diabetics, personal hygiene and reproductive health. They have to focus on community health education in prevent illness. Therefore their course should include syllabus on this matter and more importantly how it should be carried out successfully.

Conclusion

Medical education in India needs to transform to be meaningful for our people. For this, the health agenda need to be accorded importance in governance. Absence of a clear vision, a concerted effort by all stakeholders, and a strong political leadership in the area of medical education are the significant causes for the slow progress toward this metamorphosis. The prime task that lies ahead for India is to work out a national medical curriculum which caters to our country's needs.

Accreditation of medical institutions and quality assurance in their functioning needs attention. Inadequate doctors, thenursing shortage and the high patient to nurse ratio can

jeopardise the quality of care and patient safety in hospitals, so the government and private sectors should escalate the number of colleges. The aim of these professional courses must be to produce doctors with social responsibility. It is time to review the structure of rural health services and tailor the education to meet these needs.

*The curriculum of health professional courses and training offered in India must be designed to improve the competency covering various aspects. Regarding health education, community health educators should intensively work with the public health department, schools, government offices and even local nonprofits to design educational programs and other resources to address a community's specific needs. If the government actively engages in the above-said factors, India will reach the pinnacle in Education and Health sector.

References

Books

1. Gopalakrishnan.N, Mental Health and You, Popular Prakashan: Bombay, 1994.
2. Rashmi Soni, Health Education and Administration, Atlantic Publishers and Distributers.(P) LTD, New Delhi, 2012.

Reports

1. School Health – A Guide for Primary Health Teachers, Directorate General of Health Services, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.
2. Raju,B. , School Health Program in Selected middle schools of Delhi, A survey, New Delhi, NCERT, 1970.
3. Health Education for School-Age Children-A framework, Health education Bureau and NCERT: New Delhi.
4. The First Ten Years of WHO, Geneva1958, p, 459.
5. Bulletin on Rural Health Statistics in India. Statistics Division in India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2017.
6. India Fact sheet, National Family Health Survey – 2015- 16, NFHS. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare.
7. Bulletin of WHO Review of National survey in India.

Journals

1. Kapil Yadav, et at., “Revitalizing Rural Health Care Delivery: can Rural Health Practitioners be the answer?? Indian Journal of Community Medicine. Jan, 34 (1) 3-5, 2009.
2. Stefan Lindgren and David Gordon, “Role of the Doctorsand the competencies Expected from the Doctor of theFuture of World Fender action of Medical Education (wfme.org).
3. Madav Deo, ‘Doctor population Ratio of India the Reality’ in Indian Journal of Medical Research. 137 (4): 632-635, April-2013.
4. Sanjay Zodpa et al., Allopathy doctors in India Estimates Norms of Projections in Indian Journal of Medical Research, April 2018.
5. Medical care Recommendation 144 (No 69) InternationalLabour Organization (Preamble – 66 to 74).